

TYPES OF PHONETIC ENGLISH ACCENT IN UZBEK EDUCATION

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Annotation: Many of them have a break in learning English there are various factors leading to a decrease in motivation; this category of students lacks the skills to work independently on phonetics. The article suggests solutions problems faced by college graduates, when developing phonetic skills at university.

Key words and phrases: various factors, decrease in motivation, category of students lacks, independently on phonetics.

Now let's look at how work is being done to develop phonetic skills in Russian colleges and universities. First-year students of non-linguistic secondary vocational and higher educational institutions continuing to study English as a language first foreign language, are generally familiar with the pronunciation of English sounds, stresses, word models and intonation structures from the course of basic and secondary schools. In recent years, we have noted an increase in the quality of knowledge in a foreign language in general and the ability to correctly pronounce the most common words in the English language and understand common phrases in particular. To a large extent this in our opinion, is due to the introduction of IELTS in a foreign language. It should also be noted that in many regions of the country there are experimental sites developing the topic of lifelong education, and within the framework of the work of these sites, significant attention is paid to the quality of training of school graduates in a Foreign language in order to ensure continuity of foreign language education at the school-college and school-university levels. However, school pupils make both phonetic (which do not interfere with communication, for example, softening of consonants) and phonological errors (which change meaning of the word and thereby preventing communication, for example deafening). Despite the fact that Uzbek colleges and universities use similar methods and approaches to teaching phonics who entered the university College graduates experience certain difficulties in learning English, including pronunciation.

Firstly, these difficulties are associated with the general psychological stress experienced by a young man - a college graduate who initially prepared himself for the activity of a performer and graduated from college and then entered a university, having made the decision move to another level of education in order to expand their career prospects, often after a gap of several years. Unfortunately, in Russian universities there are very few associated with colleges programs, and, for the most part, college graduates who have already studied professionally oriented English in college have to start with "passing" in their first year at university social and everyday conversational topics together with yesterday's schoolchildren. College graduates seem to be returning back to those topics that have already been covered and forgotten. English teachers language, you should know about

this and be ready to provide psychological and pedagogical support to college graduates, especially since in a student group at a university there are usually few such students, not more than 1–2 people.

Vocabulary learned by college students includes names objects and processes of future activities in working professions. Lexical topics studied by students of related specialties at the university are mainly related to economics and management.

Teaching English phonetics hotel and restaurant enterprise (complex), new developments and prospects for the development of the industry. In essence, the language of each specialty has its own characteristics. For example, the lexical minimum for specialties related to hotel and restaurant services includes many words, came from the French language: cuisine [kwɪ'zi:n] kitchen (food,culinary arts); haute cuisine [ˌøʊt kwɪ'zi:n] haute cuisine; sumptuous ['sʌmptʃuəs] luxurious, expensive; gracious ['ɡreɪʃəs] nice; café ['kæfeɪ] cafe; restaurant ['rest(ə)rɒnt] restaurant; banquet ['bæŋkwɪt] banquet, dinner party; menu ['menju:] menu; chef [ʃef] chef; à la carte [ˌɑː la: 'kɑː(r)t] from the menu (that is, not a combination dinner); table d'hôte [ˌtɑːb(ə)l 'dəʊt] set lunch, table d'hôte; gourmet ['ɡʊə(r)meɪ] gourmet, connoisseur and lover of delicious food; soufflé ['suːfleɪ] soufflé; fondant ['fɒndənt] fondant, mastic; champagne [ʃæm'peɪn] champagne; bourbon ['bɜː(r)bən] bourbon; sauté ['səuteɪ] saute (frying, sautéing).

Reading such words does not follow the rules of reading in English language, and this is somewhat confusing for students. For teachers English speakers should repeat the classic rules of reading with college graduates continuing their studies at the university. It is also necessary to immediately, during the first lesson at the university, explain the features of the vocabulary of the specialty language. Thirdly, problems in the field of phonetics that arise among college graduates are associated with the overall amount of independent work in English in college compared to university. In college Only a few hours are allotted for independent work (about 20 hours for the entire course of study), and the university provides for extracurricular independent work in the amount of 50% of the teaching time. University students independently prepare messages and reports for presentations at conferences, develop the content of roles for participation in role-playing and business games. At the same time, they should be able to work not only on the content side of their speech, but also on pronunciation.

Since continuity in education is a bidirectional process, of course, not only university teachers, but also college teachers should be involved in it. For more successful adaptation to studying at a university and the formation of the ability to independently work on the phonetic side of college students' speech is necessary introduce the Internet dictionary and develop a habit of using it. In this dictionary, phonetic transcriptions are given for words in the English language, at the same time. You can see the meaning of a particular word in uzbek. Listening to and understanding authentic audio materials can be problematic for those students who cannot identify one word or another in the flow of speech, so a good assistant in working on phonetics is the MacMillan dictionary - www.macmillandictionary.com. This online dictionary has the ability listening in isolation and remembering the pronunciation of each word. We offer college students the following exercises:

how to: prepare reading and translation of small texts or fragments texts, write down unfamiliar words with transcription and translation, listen to the pronunciation of these

words in the MacMillan dictionary, divide the sentences into semantic groups and highlight in each group stressed word.

Such assignments serve the purpose of preparing college students for university studies. Check homework completion you can use the game "Phonetic Dominoes". As an example, Figure 1 shows cards for checking pronunciation difficult words from a text containing information about the restaurant Daniel <https://www.danielnyc.com/about> (cards in the student audience can be used without phonetic transcription). The students' task is to combine words with the same reading of vowels or consonants sounds. On the playing field of each card, the letters "c" and "v" indicate you need to search by vowel (v – vowel) or consonant (c – consonant) correspondence. Then we ask students to read in pairs words that have the same sounds.

Thus, teaching phonetics to students of uzbek colleges and universities has a lot in common: the presence of an accompanying course phonetics, inclusion in this course of theoretical material, traditional and game phonetic exercises, widespread use information and communication technologies. Teaching pronunciation in college and university carries out using similar methods and teaching methods. Problems in pronunciation among college graduates continuing their studies at a university are associated with psychological tension during the transition to a new, higher level of education.

A break in training, differences in the lexical composition of the English language course program in college and university, and more amount of extracurricular independent work. The work of an English language teacher at a university should include aspects aimed at overcoming difficulties and developing correct pronunciation at a new level: psychological support college graduates, explaining the features of the specialty language, compiling lists of sites for working on phonetics, recommendations for working with such sites. English teachers language colleges should teach their students how to independently work on the phonetic side of speech.

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